

PSYCHOGRAPHIC SEGMENTATION: THE DIRECT PATH OF MEDIA AND ADVERTISING TO THE AUDIENCE

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Abstract

The methods of producing and mass-distributing information that have increased exponentially over the last 40 years appear favorable to the media and to advertising entities. However, this turned out to be a double-edged sword: the information flood forced individuals to close the "valves" of the channels through which incoming information passes into their consciousness. This has created a new type of difficulty for the media and other "broadcasters of information." One way to overcome these obstacles is to account for the structuring of recipients into groups according to their psychographic characteristics. These specifics become increasingly decisive as to whether and which information the individual will admit into their mind.

Keywords: communication; mass media; psychographic profiles; psychology; segmentation; information overload; advertising; audience; consumer behavior; longitudinal research

Introduction

Never before in the history of human civilization has the individual been confronted with such a challenge. The very capacity of the human being as a biological organism is put to the test. The obvious limits of the human individual's ability to process information are well known: "Our nervous system is not capable of processing more than 110 bits of information per second. Just to hear me and understand what I'm saying, you need to process 60 bits per second. That's why you can't understand more than two people talking to you at the same time." (Csikszentmihalyi, n.d.)

In contemporary conditions, at one and the same moment an individual is being "spoken to" simultaneously by far more than two people: the people they are communicating with at that moment, the notification of a new email on the computer, the social network alert on the phone, the radio, and so on. Subjected to unceasing and heavy informational pressure, the individual is compelled to find a way to navigate the ever-growing number of information sources. The tendency of a dizzying increase in the individual's negative experiences was noted in its earliest stages, diagnosed, and flagged with a warning sign. This leads to Zygmunt Bauman's conclusion: "The possibilities of informal communication have remained largely unchanged since at least the Paleolithic, and cheap communication floods and suffocates memory, instead of nourishing and stabilizing it." (Bauman, 1998)

The process of an avalanche of information crashing down on the individual has no chance of slowing its pace. Experts show very precisely what the curve of information growth looks like: "90% of the world's information has been created in the last 2 years. And every two years, the volume of data in the world doubles." (Bartley, 2023)

It is obvious that under this pressure, individuals increasingly and persistently close the "valves" of the channels through which they receive information into their consciousness. This places the media and advertising entities in an ever more difficult position, as they are forced to fight ever harder in the ever denser jungle of information through which the recipient's consciousness wanders. Traditional methods of "breaking through" to consciousness are becoming less and less effective, compelling a farewell to familiar methods and instruments of communication and a turn toward new, more appropriate ones. One of these instruments is segmentation through the Psychographic Profiles of the population/consumers/audience.

1. Reasons for Seeking a New Approach in Communication

There is further evidence for the search for effective mechanisms against the information that exceeds individuals' capacities for receiving and processing it. This evidence is found not only among the "addressees" of information, but also among the "broadcasters": the entities that seek to present themselves, to remind addressees of their existence, and to prompt certain behavior favorable to the "broadcasters." In the relationship between "sending information" and "protection from excessive information," the same principle operates as in the opposition between a sword and a shield. The "broadcasters" attempt to deliver an informational blow, while the "valves on communication channels" seek to protect the consciousness of individuals. The effectiveness of the "valves" is increasingly widely accepted as very high, because the "broadcasters" were compelled to begin taking them into account and to seek ways of overcoming them. The strength of these valves is evidently so considerable that the "broadcasters" were forced not only to acknowledge their existence and to reckon with their resistance, but also to invest gigantic efforts in overcoming them.

In customary practice prior to the advent of electronic communication, "broadcasters" sought to exploit the structuring of individuals according to socio-demographic characteristics. An

emanation of this principle is the "25-54 rule": in peplemeter data (measuring television audiences), to this day the primary focus is on results reflecting a specific age group, with this range being the most frequently used by advertisers in planning their campaigns.

However, the pursuit of the "demographic trace" in the contemporary situation of an information avalanche appears increasingly unproductive. If we lean on the theory of "flow" in positive psychology as a pathway to explaining the mechanisms through which the individual responds to the communication challenge, we will find that "The experience of flow is universal and is found in all classes, genders, age groups, and cultures and can be felt during the performance of many types of activities." (Oppland, 2016)

Leaving behind the previous approach based on socio-demographic characteristics, we move directly toward the psychological characteristics of the personality and the probability of discovering common traits for certain groups. It seems particularly rational to orient ourselves toward the Psychographic Profiles of individuals.

2. The Segmentation Model Through Psychographic Profiles of the Population

The topic of Psychographic Profiles developed in the intermediate period encompassing the apex of mass communication in the previous "electric" stage of communication (most often associated with the power of television) and the creation of the scientific and technical preconditions for the emergence of the electronic stage. Already then, researchers clearly emphasized that "The term 'psychography' [refers to] studies which place a comparatively strong emphasis on generalized personality traits." (W. Thomas Anderson, 1984) The authors further outline: "The term psychographic connotes the profiling of psychological processes or properties. The domain of psychographic research is set apart in terms of cognitive style — cognitive processes or properties, including values, attitudes, beliefs, opinions, interests — which can be systematically related to characteristic patterns of overt behavior."

According to widely accepted understanding, psychographic profiling refers to the segmentation of certain groups in society through the study of cognitive characteristics such as the attitudes, interests, opinions, and beliefs of the personality. These characteristics do not have a single manifestation observable only in one specific area. It seems far more rational to accept that the personality is "permeated" by such general characteristics in all its interactions with the information it receives — presupposing the potential for discovering rational elements of segmentation according to the mechanisms through which the individual responds to the information tsunami as a whole.

It is obvious that such structuring could be carried out through targeted research. But this task also has an equally important practical purpose: the applied instrument must be practically usable under conditions requiring rapid application. This means building a methodology that would allow outlining the profiles of a small number of groups — but with sufficiently distinct individual features — while the specifics of communication toward them take into account the need for action in comparatively short timeframes acceptable to "broadcasters," whether in the public or private sector.

Over 130 nationally representative sociological surveys of the adult population of Bulgaria, conducted in the period 2011-2023 by Progress Consult, established that it is indeed possible to structure the population into groups according to their psychographic characteristics; that these groups number only 4 — but are strongly differentiated from each other; and that their approach to receiving information (media, advertising) is founded on common principles but operates on the basis of the psychographic characteristics specific to each group.

These four groups can be briefly described with their main individual characteristics:

SEEKERS

The most self-confident and risk-prone group. Emotions are one of the most strongly distinguishing features: no other group has members who experience such a high degree of desire to indulge in pleasures and excitements (and therefore to pay for them). Due to the fact that they are the most willing to take risks and have the highest degree of self-confidence, Seekers have the greatest desire of all to try new things. They are notably the most optimistic about life. They tend toward collectivism and feel very comfortable in a group. The opinions of others are not decisive, but are nonetheless important to them.

MEMBERS

They seek mostly warm relationships with others. Insufficiently self-confident, partly prone to risky actions. Emotions and entertainment are not the most essential thing for them. They do not uncritically conform their opinion with referents or those around them, but display a certain autonomy. Nevertheless, they feel better when following someone else's decision or when someone expresses approval of their actions. They prefer comfort — including in group relations — over creating difficulties.

SOLITARY

To the lowest degree of all, they are interested in the opinions of others — and also in what others think of their opinions. Absolutely convinced of their sole rightness, their own opinion is for them an irrefutable law. Accustomed to relying on themselves in all circumstances, they are almost not influenced by the majority opinion. They find security in themselves, in their abilities, in their opinion — not in belonging to some group. They are attracted to sharper clashes and clearly expressed confrontation — because such scenes prove that whoever "cannot" deserves to be defeated.

BALL BEARINGS

The most insecure and cautious of all. The absolute prerequisite for them is to feel security by fitting into a group. They show the most pronounced tendency among all to comply with the opinions of others (referents). The key concept for them is Security; they look for an axis around which to "revolve" and are less inclined to "break away" from it. They are the most cautious consumers, combining very hard time taking any risks with comparatively low self-confidence. Emotions have extremely low importance: they are the most pragmatic group, strongly influenced at the point of purchase by promotions and discounts.

The application of the described methodology unambiguously shows that the population's relationship to types of media, specific media, and specific advertisements is based to a greater extent on psychographic rather than demographic characteristics.

3. The Reflection of Psychographic Characteristics in the Reception of Media and Advertising

Grouping according to Psychographic Profiles represents a structuring according to the presence of similar traits in the essence of individual personalities. These traits manifest in

preferences for certain product or price categories, specific brands, cultural phenomena, and mass media. What is particularly clearly evident is that every brand, medium, or advertisement "draws" toward itself precisely certain consumers belonging to a greater extent to a given group according to Psychographic Profiles. This dominance is caused by the signals that — both currently and historically — a given brand or entity has been sending to the multitude of individuals. Those consumers have identified the source as "like themselves," and have therefore "attached" to it together with other "like themselves."

Particularly telling are the strongly specific characteristics of individual groups when the level of use of individual entities (consumer behavior) is compared with the degree to which consumers have noticed and remembered television advertising of those same entities.

For a fuller understanding of these ratios, we must first examine to what extent the groups use television as an information channel at all:

Source: Progress Consult, nationally representative survey of adult population of Bulgaria, direct personal interviews, n=1030 (November 2019)

The first thing clearly visible is that while in three of the groups the use of television as an information channel is comparatively similar (and in two — Seekers and Ball Bearings — practically identical), the Solitary group specifically displays weaker interest in this channel. But this is characteristic of them not only during the specific survey: repeatedly conducted surveys over the years consistently show that the Solitary group in principle pays less attention to this information channel:

*Source: Progress Consult, nationally representative surveys of adult population of Bulgaria, direct personal interviews.
2013: n=1049; 2015: n=1049; 2017: n=1039; 2019: n=1030*

Given such a consistently stable relationship toward television, if only the level of exposure mattered (the mass of advertisements reaching recipients), the degree of recall should at least approximately replicate the ratios in television viewing. Nothing of the sort is observed — quite the opposite: the proportions of recall of advertisements for individual banks differ dramatically from the ratios in television viewing in general:

Source: Progress Consult, nationally representative survey of adult population of Bulgaria, direct personal interviews, n=1030 (November 2019)

Obvious is, for example, the cardinal difference in the degree to which the Solitary group perceives FIB's television advertising compared to all other banks. As already noted, the Solitary in principle watch television less than other groups. Yet it is precisely they who, far more often than other groups, noticed FIB's advertising — moreover, this is the only case in which the Solitary have in the greatest relative proportion remembered the advertising of any bank. Consequently, it is not the volume of advertising that reached consumers, but rather its specific "resonance" that was detected by people who actively opened their valves to admit information they registered as closest to their own essence.

Evidence that individuals are very clearly structured into groups that react differently to different signals is unambiguously provided by data gathered through the application of the Psychographic Profile methodology in peplemeter measurement. [1]

Psychographic Profiles and Film Preferences

Source: Nielsen Admosphere, 2018

In the realm of the most "pure" entertainment — film — the inevitable orientation of individual groups toward specific signals that best correspond to their essence is revealed in much clearer form. In this direct comparison between two films broadcast at the same time, it is clearly registered that 3 of the groups according to Psychographic Profiles gave their preference to the action film. Among the Solitary in particular, even greater interest was observed — which is in complete accordance with some of the most principal characteristics of their profile. Being extraordinarily self-convinced of their original rightness and abilities, the Solitary enjoy watching battles, clashes, rivalry, and competition — because it is pleasant for them to see how the strong win, while the weak are "beaten" deservedly.

The behavior of the Members is exactly the opposite. They are absolutely the only group that in greater part chose to watch the romantic comedy — which is in complete accord with their leading features. Members are the greatest adherents of comfort in its everyday sense. They are repelled by any form of tension, dueling, bleeding, or suffering. As a result, they 2.5 times more often than the Solitary preferred to watch the romantic comedy rather than the spy action film.

Psychographic Profiles and Reality TV

Source: Nielsen Admosphere, 2018

With the evident dominance of MasterChef among 3 of the groups, it is noteworthy that the Solitary group to a greater extent preferred the rival show Hell's Kitchen. Moreover, their share is 30% larger than the corresponding share of the Members who watched the same program. The reason lies in the philosophy of the show itself: its aggressive, tense character appeals to the Solitary because of their baseline characteristics, but for precisely the same reason repels the Members.

Psychographic Profiles and Sports

Of particular importance is the orientation of individual groups toward sports broadcasts, because in it is revealed their relationship to a completely different broad area — sport as a whole. Even a single example is sufficient to understand how powerfully the individual groups differ in their preferences for different sports:

Source: Nielsen Atmosphere, 2018

When it comes to watching court tennis, we are not dealing with mere differences — but with a monstrous gulf in the interest of individual groups. In reality, only the Solitary demonstrate enthusiasm for it. The reason is absolutely the same as described for films or reality shows: the very essence of court tennis is connected with strikes; literally every minute there is a winner and a loser — and such signals are precisely what the Solitary seek.

Very expressive in this regard is also the Solitary's interest in volleyball. At first glance it appears incongruous with their essence — since they in principle dislike "mass" events (which is why, for example, they least of all stay at all-inclusive hotels — so as not to mingle with the "crowd"). The reason is that volleyball satisfies one of their main features: seeing someone defeated as often as possible. In volleyball, someone constantly and rhythmically wins a point while another loses one; a volleyball match cannot end in a draw — there is always a winner in the end.

The Hammer of Concepts and Psychographic Profiles

The meaning of information is perceived by the individual through the concepts it carries. If the concepts are incomprehensible or mismatched with their essential features — the valves of the communication channels to their consciousness will be closed.

The concepts in information can be presented through various expressive means: images, sounds, situations, and words. Each of these instruments individually can have decisive significance. For example: if a video clip contains only one character — it will be perceived more favorably by a corresponding group; the same group, however, will show resistance toward a video clip containing more than one character. When it comes to situational content: one group will react far more favorably if the plot is woven from struggle, confrontation, rivalry, and tension — while another group will literally turn away from such a situation.

In the majority of cases, however, what is most fatally important is the word. One of the most specific features of the human being as a species is precisely this: that they perceive concepts through words. This is why what is decisive is the exact words through which concepts are conveyed — so as to reach the maximum number of recipients most successfully. Evidence for the stability in the perception of specific concepts — making it possible for them to be effectively used in building messages — is provided by a long time series of studies among the adult population of Bulgaria: [2]

Source: Progress Consult, nationally representative surveys of adult population of Bulgaria, direct personal interviews. April 2016: n=898; May 2017: n=1035; November 2018: n=1015; November 2019: n=1030; December 2022: n=803 (urban population)

Source: Progress Consult, see Figure on "Energy" for full survey details.

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A comparative examination of the results clearly shows that the Seekers group is the most "susceptible" to the perception of all concepts — which is a reflection of this group's higher propensity to inform itself and interact with the environment. It is also established that the concept of "Energy" works weakest among the Ball Bearings, while the concepts of "Family" and "Prestige" work weakest among the Solitary. Consequently, if any entity constructs its messages to the indicated groups on the basis of these concepts — it is actually single-handedly closing the "valves" to the consciousness of those groups. The necessity of knowing the structure of the relevant population imperatively imposes the requirement for close examination of its psychographic characteristics, since the primary task of communication is, after all, to avoid possible errors — and only in second place to create effective messages.

Conclusion

The difficulties in communication related to its insufficient effectiveness provoked attempts to solve the problem. One of the totally applied and loudly acclaimed approaches was to "escape" from mass, impersonal communication and to move toward its opposite. This is why instruments were created through which to achieve alignment with certain objective elements of the actions of the specific individual. "Cookies" represent an attempt to solve this task, since they show what the actual actions of the individual are. However, this approach rests on experience (what the individual has searched for) and benefit (the presumption that they will again need something similar). It totally ignores the topic of the essential, deepest traits of the personality — and consequently entirely turns its back on the question of whether and how one speaks to that personality in a way that will almost automatically open the valves of their communication channels.

Insofar as the effective dissemination of information cannot be carried out by taking into account the characteristics of each individual, the rational approach is to establish the potential grouping of the mass of individuals into a clearly measurable structure. The need to achieve

communication effectiveness through grouping of some kind is obvious, which gives grounds for experts such as Seth Godin to summarize: "We don't care if all of them look the same, but it will be truly useful if you have some way of grouping them... Demographic or — more likely — psychographic characteristics?" (Godin, 2018)

The answer to this question in the previous stage of civilization's development was unequivocal: "demographic." At the end of the 20th and beginning of the 21st century, however, the need arose to reconsider this assertion. From the perspective of the mass media and advertising entities at this stage, segmentation through the Psychographic Profiles of the population appears far more effective — offering richer possibilities for reaching the consciousness of recipients.

Notes

[1] In 2017, the methodology for defining population groups according to their Psychographic Profiles was implemented in the Nielsen Admosphere peoplemeter system in Bulgaria, at the suggestion of media agency Argent. The panelists included in it were individually defined as belonging to a specific Psychographic Profile. This made it possible to observe with complete objectivity what the preferences of viewers from each group were toward specific television channels, types of programs, and specific programs. These observations demonstrated the enormous extent to which the attitudes and orientations of representatives of individual profiles differ — and how effectively information can be targeted toward them when constructed in accordance with their profile.

[2] Data in this section are from the following series of Progress Consult surveys: April 2016, n=898; May 2017, n=1035; November 2018, n=1015; November 2019, n=1030; December 2022, n=803 (adult urban population of Bulgaria, direct personal interviews).

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About the Author

Rossen Koutelov is Doctor of Sociology (UNWE Sofia, 2025) and founder of Progress Consult (est. 1996), a Bulgarian marketing research and consulting agency. His doctoral dissertation, "Psychographic Profiles and Consumer Behavior," developed an original longitudinal

methodology for psychographic segmentation validated through 13 nationally representative surveys (n=12,904, Bulgaria 2013-2023), identifying four stable psychographic groups: Seekers, Members, Solitary, and Ball Bearings.

This paper presents the empirical application of that methodology to media measurement and advertising recall — demonstrating how psychographic group membership determines which media content individuals admit to their consciousness, independently of demographic characteristics.

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